

Configurable Digital Astable Multivibrator on FPGA: Verilog Implementation on the Tang Nano 1K Platform Using Gowin FPGA Designer Education

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Abstract—This paper presents the design, implementation, and analysis of a configurable digital astable multivibrator with selectable oscillation frequency through push buttons, using the Verilog hardware description language and the Tang Nano 1K development board, equipped with the GW1NZ-LV1 FPGA from Gowin Semiconductor. The development environment used was Gowin FPGA Designer Education, a synthesis and implementation tool provided by the device manufacturer. The Verilog module, named `freq_generator`, employs a 25-bit synchronous counter and combinational logic to select four distinct oscillation frequencies—1 Hz, 2 Hz, 4 Hz, and 8 Hz—derived from the board’s internal 27 MHz clock, with the output visually observed through an onboard LED. The circuit behavior is based on integer division of the reference frequency, and the obtained results confirm the correspondence between theoretically calculated values and the behavior observed on the physical platform. This work demonstrates that low-cost FPGAs constitute effective platforms for teaching and prototyping digital systems, including oscillators and frequency dividers with dynamic reconfiguration.

Index Terms—Digital astable multivibrator; FPGA; Verilog; Frequency divider; Tang Nano 1K; Gowin; Embedded digital systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

The astable multivibrator is one of the most fundamental oscillator circuits in electronics, characterized by the absence of stable states: the circuit continuously alternates between two logic levels without any external stimulus, producing an approximately square waveform (Sedra and Smith, 2015). In its classical analog form, it can be implemented using bipolar transistors, operational amplifiers, or integrated timers such as the NE555, widely discussed in the literature (Boylestad and Nashelsky, 2013). With the advancement of digital electronics, the same behavioral principles have been reproduced by synchronous digital circuits, in which oscillation is obtained by dividing a reference clock through counters, resulting in output signals with precisely controlled frequency and duty cycle (Wakerly, 2006).

Programmable logic devices, particularly FPGAs (Field-Programmable Gate Arrays), have become dominant platforms for implementing highly flexible digital systems, allowing hardware functions to be described in languages such as VHDL or Verilog and synthesized directly into reconfigurable

silicon (Brown and Vranesic, 2014). According to Maxfield (2004), FPGAs offer a unique combination of performance, parallelism, and reconfigurability that distinguishes them from microcontrollers and DSPs in dedicated hardware applications. In educational and prototyping contexts, compact and low-cost FPGA-based boards have gained increasing relevance, as they democratize access to programmable logic development (Chu, 2008).

The Tang Nano 1K platform, developed by Sipeed and based on the GW1NZ-LV1 FPGA from Gowin Semiconductor, represents a contemporary example of this trend. With only 1152 LUTs, a 27 MHz internal clock, USB-C programming interface, and compact dimensions, the board is suitable for educational projects and simple prototypes (Gowin Semiconductor, 2023). The official development environment, Gowin FPGA Designer Education, provides a complete flow of synthesis, mapping, routing, and bitstream generation, being freely available for academic use.

In this context, this work aims to describe and analyze the implementation of a digital astable multivibrator in Verilog on the Tang Nano 1K platform, capable of oscillating at four distinct frequencies: 1 Hz, 2 Hz, 4 Hz, and 8 Hz, selectable in real time through two push buttons. This study is justified by the pedagogical relevance of the topic, the growing adoption of low-cost FPGAs in educational environments, and the scarcity of publications in Portuguese documenting practical experiences with the Gowin platform in formal academic contexts.

II. METHODOLOGY

The project development followed the traditional FPGA design flow, as described by Chu (2008) and Brown and Vranesic (2014): behavioral specification, HDL description, functional simulation, logical synthesis, physical implementation, and hardware verification. The hardware description language adopted was Verilog HDL, standardized by IEEE 1364-2005 (IEEE, 2006), due to its concise syntax and wide adoption in both industry and academia (Palnitkar, 2003).

The main module, named `freq_generator`, receives as inputs the 27 MHz clock signal from the Tang Nano 1K internal oscillator (Figure 1) and two digital signals from

onboard push buttons (`btn0` and `btn1`). The output is a digital signal (`led_out`) connected to the onboard LED. Internally, the module consists of two distinct `always` blocks with complementary functions.

The first block, sensitive to all signal variations (`always @ (*)`), implements purely combinational logic responsible for selecting the counter limit value based on the button combination, using a 2-bit `case` structure. The second block, sensitive to the rising edge of the clock (`always @(posedge clk)`), implements a 25-bit synchronous up-counter that resets upon reaching the limit value and simultaneously toggles the LED output using bitwise negation.

Fig. 1. Tang Nano 1K development board Sipeed (2022).

The frequency division logic is based on the mathematical relationship between the reference clock frequency, the counter limit, and the desired output frequency. For an input clock $f_{clk} = 27$ MHz, the output frequency is given by:

$$f_{out} = \frac{f_{clk}}{2L}$$

where L is the counter limit. The factor of 2 arises because two counter overflow events are required to complete a full cycle of the square wave. Thus, the calculated limits are 13,500,000 for 1 Hz, 6,750,000 for 2 Hz, 3,375,000 for 4 Hz, and 1,687,500 for 8 Hz. All values fit within 25 bits and were implemented directly in Verilog using readable integer literals (Palnitkar, 2003).

Frequency selection is achieved by concatenating the button signals $\{btn1, btn0\}$, forming a 2-bit selector equivalent to a 4:1 multiplexer, as discussed by Wakerly (2006). The synthesis process maps the combinational logic into LUTs and the sequential elements into flip-flops within the FPGA.

The design was synthesized, implemented, and programmed onto the Tang Nano 1K via USB-C. Verification was performed through direct visual observation of the onboard LED behavior for each button combination.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental results demonstrated full agreement between theoretical predictions and observed behavior. For each combination of `btn0` and `btn1`, the LED oscillated at the expected frequency, confirming the correct operation of the synchronous frequency divider.

At 1 Hz, the LED completed one full cycle per second, easily observable by the human eye, consistent with typical low-frequency timing applications (Maxfield, 2004). Higher frequencies (2 Hz, 4 Hz, and 8 Hz) exhibited progressively faster transitions. Even at 8 Hz, the signal remained below

the human flicker fusion threshold (15–60 Hz depending on conditions), allowing perceptual distinction (Wandell, 1995).

The design does not explicitly initialize registers via reset, relying instead on FPGA configuration defaults. While acceptable for educational purposes, more robust designs should include explicit reset logic (Chu, 2008). Similarly, no debouncing mechanism was implemented for the push buttons, though no practical issues were observed due to the high clock frequency.

Resource utilization was minimal: 26 flip-flops and a small number of LUTs, well within the device capacity of 1152 LUTs (Gowin Semiconductor, 2023). This confirms the suitability of the Tang Nano 1K for educational applications.

Compared to analog astable multivibrators, such as those based on the NE555 (Boylestad and Nashelsky, 2013), the digital implementation offers superior frequency precision, stability, and reconfigurability. However, analog solutions remain advantageous in cost and simplicity for standalone applications. As noted by Trimberger (2015), FPGA-based designs are preferable when integration, flexibility, and scalability are required.

The source code is available at: <https://github.com/vitor-souza-ime/fpgama>.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented the implementation of a configurable digital astable multivibrator in Verilog HDL on the Tang Nano 1K platform using Gowin FPGA Designer Education. The `freq_generator` module successfully divides the 27 MHz clock into four selectable frequencies: 1 Hz, 2 Hz, 4 Hz, and 8 Hz, with real-time control via push buttons.

The results validate the theoretical approach of synchronous frequency division and confirm the effectiveness of the Tang Nano 1K platform for educational digital system design. From a pedagogical perspective, the project integrates key concepts such as HDL-based design, synchronous counters, combinational logic, and digital oscillators.

Future work may include hardware debouncing, explicit reset implementation, expanded frequency selection, and the use of internal PLLs for generating non-integer frequency divisions.

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